

PROPOSALS FOR IMPLEMENTING DUAL EDUCATION IN THE HIGHER
EDUCATION SYSTEM

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna

Director of Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute, PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate
Professor, sadoqats@mail.ru, cellphone.: +998 91 441-49-10

Annotatsion. This article presents suggestions for implementing dual education in the higher education system. The dual education model is an effective method of teaching that combines theoretical knowledge with practical skills. The article offers proposals for the implementation of this system in Uzbekistan, analyzes its advantages, challenges, and solutions based on scientific research. It also highlights international experiences in the field of dual education.

Keywords: dual education, higher education system, practical skills, theoretical knowledge, employment, international experiences, education and industry integration.

Dual education is a method of education based on the integration of educational and production processes, in which students are given practical skills along with theoretical knowledge. The introduction of dual education is important in the process of modernization of the higher education system in Uzbekistan. This method not only helps students to work, but also creates an opportunity for employers to train qualified personnel. Dual education also involves conducting training simultaneously with production, showing students real working conditions. The dual education system gives students the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. This, in turn, leads to a high level of readiness for work, strengthening the relationship between young personnel and employers. Students have the opportunity to master production processes, service provision or other specific tasks in practice, which facilitates their learning.

Let's consider the opinions of our domestic scientists on the proposals for the organization of dual education. Scientists see dual education among the new educational models. M. Muradov in his study gives a general description of dual education, emphasizing its theoretical and practical integration. This system allows students to apply theoretical knowledge to acquire production and practical skills. Dual education, undoubtedly, is shown as an effective tool for the complete modernization of the process of training for work, personnel training [5].

Scientists also pay attention to the importance of dual education for the economy. In a study conducted by a foreign scientist M. Johnson, they recognize the role of dual education in training the most important qualified personnel in the production and service sectors. In addition, scientists show the impact of dual education on the country's economy, the possibility of creating more stable jobs for young people who are promoted to work [3].

In particular, one of the scientists of our republic, A. Akhmedov, in his study, emphasized that one of the main problems in implementing dual education in higher education institutions is the need for employers to adapt to the requirements. It is obvious that weak cooperation between employers and educational institutions can reduce the effectiveness of dual education. Also, problems are indicated in the programs for training specialists, aimed at strengthening the integration of practical and theoretical knowledge [1].

For the effective implementation of the dual education system in the higher education system, specific proposals have been developed based on a number of studies and the opinions of scientists. For

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

example, T. Kalimullaev recommends creating new forms of cooperation between production and higher education institutions for dual education [4]. In his opinion, it is necessary to create new platforms to expand the opportunities for interaction between employers and educational institutions and internships in production. Furthermore, M. Raev [6] considers the support of the state and private sectors to be important in the implementation of dual education. According to his research, it is necessary to establish a system of financial support for educational institutions by the state and subsidies for part of the income of employers.

The results of the implementation of the dual education system in different countries are well observed. In Germany and Switzerland, the dual education system has shown high efficiency not only in higher education, but also in vocational education. A. Gutman [2] points to the experiences of Germany and Switzerland as the best ways to implement their own dual education systems in higher education. The dual education system in Germany allows students to learn theoretical and practical knowledge at the same time. Students are successful in adapting to the production environment for production and practice. Also, the dual education system in Switzerland is effective with state support for systematic support for the employment of young people.

Suggestions for the organization of dual education in higher education are important for the modernization of the state's education system, economic development, and improving the quality and efficiency of personnel training. Dual education is a method of education that combines study and production, inextricably linking practical and theoretical knowledge. There are a number of proposals for the introduction of this educational model at the government level. Strengthening cooperation between education and production, that is, signing cooperation agreements between higher education institutions and employers (enterprises, industrial sectors), developing special dual education programs and training modules, and ensuring their compliance with the requirements of production and practice.

In order to integrate production experience into the educational process, it is necessary to organize internships in higher educational institutions, bring it closer to the production system, and introduce advanced training programs in universities and colleges in cooperation with production organizations. In terms of the legislative development of dual education, it is necessary to establish the legal basis of dual education and adopt laws and regulations to ensure its successful operation, and develop mechanisms that regulate interaction between production and educational institutions. So as to harmonize higher education institutions and industrial enterprises, that is, to create opportunities for students to learn innovations and requirements in production, and to increase the effectiveness of dual education, it is essential to consider and provide a clear solution to the issues of providing students with a percentage of their salary or scholarships during internships at enterprises.

Improving the quality of education, in particular, the dual education model allows students to obtain more practical and production-related knowledge through the coordination of study and work processes. The issue of financing and resource allocation is being considered, it is important to create a budgetary financing mechanism for the implementation of dual education and plan to attract production sectors and organizations, provide comprehensive support to production and educational institutions, and promote innovations and technical processes.

It is also important to involve regional authorities in production, including recognizing their contribution to the integration of production and education and creating new opportunities for them, as well as implementing dual education programs in the regions and providing them with support. It is necessary to develop the workforce and promote a new type of vocational education, namely the

dual education model, to improve skills, expand the orientation of the workforce, and provide students with a wide range of jobs and opportunities, especially in industrial and innovative sectors.

It is vital to popularize dual education internationally, including by studying international experiences and implementing the dual education method in regional cooperation and international projects, developing a mechanism for encouraging active students, and introducing a system for determining the status of students in the enterprise (category, grade, etc.) based on the quality of their knowledge based on the results of dual education. These proposals should also be developed in a comprehensive manner to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of introducing dual education into the higher education system.

Long-term plans for the organization of dual education in technical higher education should be aimed at improving the quality of higher education and training personnel in accordance with the goals of the country's socio-economic development. A number of long-term plans are being developed in Uzbekistan to introduce and improve dual education. These plans may cover the following main areas:

1. The following can be said about the creation of a legal framework for dual education.

- improving legislation, that is, developing laws and regulatory legal acts necessary for the effective implementation of dual education, these laws should be aimed at regulating cooperation between the educational and industrial sectors, establishing legal frameworks for students to conduct work practice and improve their skills;
- supporting and monitoring the conclusion of contracts and agreements, that is, contracts and agreements on dual education between higher educational institutions and industrial enterprises.

2. It is mandatory to resolve the issue of expanding cooperation with production.

- cooperation with employers – to establish clear and effective cooperation with industrial sectors and enterprises to implement the dual education system, and to provide students with clear ideas about production processes and practical experience through cooperation with enterprises;
- job creation – creating jobs and practical experience areas for students through the introduction of dual education, the introduction of integrated programs of special production and education.

3. Modernization of the education system is also important. In particular:

- development of curricula suitable for dual education – development and adaptation of educational programs to socio-economic requirements, for this it is necessary to prepare educational modules and courses in higher educational institutions that meet the specific requirements and trends of production;
- development of educational technologies – introduction of educational technologies suitable for dual education (distance learning, interactive learning), which will allow students to perfectly master not only theoretical knowledge, but also production and practical skills during the educational process.

4. Training and advanced training of pedagogical personnel:

- Training of pedagogical personnel – to implement dual education in practice, pay special attention to the training of pedagogical personnel in universities, prepare specialists who understand

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

production processes in the field of education, and teachers who are ready to teach in the dual education system;

- Advanced training in enterprises – to strengthen the existing close ties between the education and production sectors, pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions should have the opportunity to improve their skills and gain experience in production.

5. In order to create opportunities for students, the following issues should be addressed:

- Expanding internships and jobs – creating wide opportunities for students to work in production through the implementation of dual education. This will allow students to learn advanced methods and techniques in production, as well as develop professional skills in accordance with production requirements;
- introduction of advanced training programs – providing students with new knowledge for improving their skills and working in the workplace through dual education. Introduction of special training and certification programs to strengthen skills in professions suitable for production.

6. In terms of financial and resource provision,

- creation of financing mechanisms – development of appropriate financing mechanisms for the introduction of dual education. This will help create educational and technical bases of higher education institutions suitable for dual education;
- financing of production enterprises – provision of state financial support to production enterprises aimed at participating in dual education, including covering the costs of internships.

7. Strengthening educational and awareness-raising work.

- Promoting the importance of education – conducting marketing and advocacy work to explain to the public the importance of dual education and its benefits, and to strengthen partnerships between students and employers;
- Research and monitoring – conducting scientific research to monitor the impact and effectiveness of dual education. Analyzing the results of the existing system and introducing monitoring mechanisms for its improvement.

8. Strengthening international cooperation and exchange of experience.

- study of international experience – use of international experience in the implementation of dual education, study of dual education systems in Europe and other developed countries and adaptation of their results to the country;
- international projects and programs – establishment of international cooperation and introduction of international financing and programs for the implementation of dual education.

The introduction of the dual education system serves to improve the quality of higher education and increase the number of employed personnel. This, in turn, helps to modernize various sectors of production and the economy, and ensure the overall economic development of the country. The integration of theoretical and practical knowledge of students ensures their successful work, and also creates the basis for training highly qualified personnel for employers.

Therefore, promising plans aimed at introducing dual education in higher education are an important step towards integrating the country's production and education sectors, improving the quality of

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

personnel training, developing the economy, and increasing the efficiency of the education system. For their implementation, it is necessary to clarify legal, pedagogical, and financial mechanisms.

REFERENCES:

1. Akhmedov A. (2018). "Challenges in the Implementation of Dual Education in Uzbekistan". *Journal of Education and Society*, 12(3), 45-59.
2. Gutman A. (2017). "Dual Education in Germany and Switzerland: International Experience and its Application". *European Education Review*, 9(4), 102-115.
3. Johnson M. (2019). "Dual Education Systems and Their Impact on Economic Development". *International Journal of Education and Economics*, 8(1), 22-34.
4. Kalimullayev T. (2021). "Prospects of Dual Education in Higher Education Institutions". Tashkent: National Publishing House.
5. Muradov M. (2020). "Dual Education: Theory and Practice". Tashkent: University Press.
6. Raev M. (2020). "Integration of Education and Industry in Uzbekistan": A Review of Dual Education Models. *Education and Innovation Journal*, 16(2), 78-85.